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PREGNANCY OUTCOMES OF NONIMMUNE HYDROPS FETALIS

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Hydrops fetalis is a rare and extremely dangerous condition that often results in intrauterine fetal death. For reasons of development, it is divided into two categories: immune, which is caused by incompatibility of the Rh factor or the ABO system, and non-immune, associated with any other reasons. Given that the incidence of immune hydrops fetalis has decreased due to the widespread use of Rh sensitization prophylaxis, nonimmune hydrops fetalis (NHF) has become the dominant form of hydrops fetalis. Non-immune hydrops fetalis occurs in 1 in 2500-3000 pregnancies and accounts for 90% of all cases [3,4]. Despite the improvement of methods of antenatal diagnosis and treatment, the problem does not lose its relevance in practical obstetrics and neonatology.

Non-immune hydrops fetalis is recognized as a complex polyetiological disease that can be caused by more than 150 different conditions. Despite the wide variety of causes, in 18% of cases it is not possible to determine the specific etiological factor of the disease [2].

With non-immune fetal hydrops, the miscarriage and stillbirth rate reaches 95%. The prognosis is unfavorable, but the cause of the disease and the time of onset of symptoms play an important role [1,5].

All of the above allows us to think that a clear definition of the management of patients with non-immune hydrops fetalis makes the presented problem extremely relevant and promising.

The aim of this study is to study and analyze the case history of patients with diagnosis nonimmune hydrops fetalis.

Materials and methods. The study consisted of a retrospective and prospective analysis. The retrospective study collected information on the incidence of NHF by year, causes and outcomes of the disease. In accordance with the goals and objectives of the study, participants in the prospective study were divided into 2 groups: Group 1 (20 pregnant women) consisted of pregnant women with NHF who received intrauterine treatment methods, Group 2 (22 pregnant women) consisted of pregnant women with NHF who refused from treatment.

Results. The causes of the disease were identified in 59% of cases in the retrospective group and in 86.2% of cases in the prospective group. The examination revealed chromosomal abnormalities in 9 patients, the most common of which was trisomy 21. In all cases, chromosomal abnormalities were observed in the 1st half of pregnancy. Nonimmune hydrops fetalis that occurs in early pregnancy is often associated with aneuploidy.

Another of the most common causes of nonimmune hydrops fetalis in the study was pathology of the cardiovascular system. 57.1% of them had tachyarrhythmias. A more detailed treatment regimen for nonimmune hydrops fetalis caused by tachyarrhythmias has been developed, and in all cases the tachyarrhythmias were treatable.

At the same time, in pregnant women who used active tactics, conservative therapy included antiviral treatment, immunoglobulin infusion, cardiotoxic treatment and antibacterial treatment methods. Among these treatment methods, immunoglobulin infusion was used for the first time for non-immune hydrops fetalis, which gave an effective result in 7 out of 9 patients.

In the study, 55% of fetal surgical procedures were performed, such as fetal paracentesis, thoracocentesis and amnioreduction. The resulting serous fluids were subjected to laboratory tests, based on the results of which treatment tactics were chosen.

At the next stage, pregnancy outcomes were analyzed. 27.4% of women in the study had living children. And all of them were observed in women of group 1, where active tactics were carried out.

In the period of 37-41 weeks, 45% of births occurred in the 1st group, and in the 2nd group there were no births during this period ($p < 0.001$).

Conclusion. If active management is chosen and intrauterine treatment of the fetus is used, pregnancy with non-immune hydrops fetalis should be prolonged for as long as possible, preferably until full-term pregnancy. Preterm birth with nonimmune hydrops fetalis does not improve perinatal outcomes.

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